

EXPLICIT FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATIONS OF THERMOSET AND THERMOPLASTIC SHEET COMPOSITE FORMING

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SUMMARY: Thin composite structures are intensively used in the transportation industries especially in the field of aerospace applications. In the RTM process a fibre fabric reinforcement is shaped by a drawing operation, then the resin is injected and polymerised at high temperature. Forming at high temperature plates with long fibre reinforcements and thermoplastic matrix (CFRTP) is an alternative process which have some advantages such as a shorter manufacturing time and a possible recycling. In both cases, the presentation will focus on the simulation of the drawing operation (concerning the dry fabrics in RTM process and long fibre reinforcements associated with thermoplastic matrix at high temperature for the CFRTP forming). For each process the deformation mechanisms during the forming will be studied. Mechanical models of the behaviour of the material including the main aspects are deduced. The sheet composite forming simulations are made by explicit finite element approaches developed within the Pam-Form[®] code.

KEYWORDS: Sheet Composite Forming, Textile reinforcements, RTM, CFRTP, Forming simulations, Textile finite elements.

INTRODUCTION

The use of fiber fabrics in transportation industries is increasing because it gives the possibility to reach complex shapes in a single operation, for a lighter final product. Thermoset and thermoplastic matrix are used. For thermoset matrix a prepreg fabric can be draped before polymerisation of the matrix [1][2]. The R.T.M. process consists of a drawing operation of the fabric before a resin is injected [3][4][5][6]. In both cases the forming modes of the fabrics are specific to this material and related to its woven constitution. A simulation code is then necessary to answer the two main questions of the conception stage : First, is the requested shape reachable by forming the fiber fabric? Second, what about the reinforcement directions after forming? Several codes based on geometrical approaches have been developed [2][5][6][7][8]. These methods, called fishnet algorithms, are very fast and efficient especially for the simulation of hand operated draping. Nevertheless in the case of forming with punch and die the static boundary conditions may be very important. So is the influence of the loads on the blank holder. The specifications of the fabric, i.e. the material for the warp and the weft, their respective size or the way it is woven, should be included in the analysis. The objective of the first part of the present paper is to propose a simulation method of fiber forming processes based on a finite element method, that take into account the fabric behavior and the static boundary conditions. In order to identify the behavior of the woven material, biaxial tensile tests are used. Finite elements for fabric have been proposed [9][10]. In the present approach, the finite elements are composed of elementary woven cells on which the deformation energy is added up. Finally forming simulation examples are presented. In a second part, for the simulation of thermoplastic composite with continuous fibers (CFRTP) in the forming

phase, the thermoplastic is modelled using one shell element per ply with contact and viscous friction. We propose to study the mechanical membrane behaviour of the reinforcement layers, the flexion of the plies (which is not classical due to the fibrous composition of the ply) and the re-compaction phase that permit to avoid interply porosity in the final product. Through thickness strain/stress will be introduced in the shell element formulation [11]. Some forming experimental results will be compared to the finite simulations in this case of CFRTP forming for aeronautical applications too.

SIMULATION OF FABRIC REINFORCEMENT SHAPING IN RTM PROCESS

Recalls about mechanical behaviour of fabric reinforcements

The study focuses on the forming stage of the RTM process, so the fiber fabrics do not include any resin which is not present at this stage. The deformation modes of a fabric are far from those of a metallic or composite material. The specific behaviour of woven reinforcements lie on the possible motion between the yarns themselves and between the numerous small fibers constituting a yarn. The cross section of these fibers is very small and each fiber have a very weak bending and compressive stiffness.

Fig. 1 Biaxial mechanical behaviour surface for a plane weave glass fabric

The angular variations between warp and weft yarns are large (up to 60° in some cases) and the in-plane shear stiffness are considered negligible. The mechanical behaviour of the fabric is defined by the relation between the weft and warp tension and strains. Due to weaving, this relation is biaxial. Consequently, a biaxial tensile device [12][13][14] is used in order to analyse and identify the fabric behaviour. Tensile tests carried out on fabrics in the directions of the yarns permit to obtain the biaxial mechanical behaviour surfaces (figure 1). They show a progressive hardening area before a zone of linear behavior. This non linearity concerns large strain values compared with the global behavior and occurs when the yarns under tension begin to straighten involving a decrease of the initial undulations of the fabric [15]. Some other results for different fiber fabrics can be found in [12][15].

Consequently, for an elementary woven cell constituted of fibers in warp and weft directions, defined by \mathbf{h}_1 and \mathbf{h}_2 (figure 2) which are only submitted to a tensile stress in these directions, we introduce a tensor of the tensions, defined by:

$$\mathbf{T} = T^{11} \mathbf{h}_1 \otimes \mathbf{h}_1 + T^{22} \mathbf{h}_2 \otimes \mathbf{h}_2. \quad (1)$$

With:

$$T^{11} = \int_{A_1} \sigma^{11} dS \quad , \quad T^{22} = \int_{A_2} \sigma^{22} dS \quad , \quad T^{11} \geq 0 \quad , \quad T^{22} \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

where A_1 and A_2 are the cross-section of the yarns in directions \mathbf{h}_1 et \mathbf{h}_2 .

Fig.2: An elementary woven cells

Explicit dynamic analysis for the simulation of the forming process

Most of the efficient industrial numerical codes of sheet forming processes are based on explicit dynamic methods [16, 17, 18] although sheet forming and especially fabric forming are quasi-static processes. The approach that is developed in this section is based on the simplified dynamic equation for fabric where it is checked that the dynamic effects are small (an implicit quasi static approach for fabric forming simulations has been developed in [19]).

For a woven domain made of n_{cell} elementary woven cells, the dynamic equation can be written in the following form:

$$\sum_{p=1}^{n_{cell}} {}^p \varepsilon_{11}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{11} {}^p L_1 + {}^p \varepsilon_{22}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{22} {}^p L_2 - \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot \boldsymbol{\eta} dV - \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{t} \cdot \boldsymbol{\eta} dS = - \int_{\Omega} \rho \ddot{\mathbf{u}} \boldsymbol{\eta} dV \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla \boldsymbol{\eta} / \boldsymbol{\eta} = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_u$$

Where Γ_u , is the part of the boundary with displacements are prescribed. \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{t} are the exterior prescribed volume and surface (on Γ_t) load. $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}$ is the acceleration corresponding to the displacement \mathbf{u} and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\boldsymbol{\eta})$ is the small deformation tensor in the virtual displacement $\boldsymbol{\eta}$:

$${}^p \varepsilon(\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \frac{1}{2} [\nabla({}^p \boldsymbol{\eta}) + \nabla^T({}^p \boldsymbol{\eta})] = {}^p \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p \mathbf{h}^{\alpha 0} \otimes {}^p \mathbf{h}^{\beta 0} \quad (4)$$

Introducing some damping, the discretised equation of the motion is

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_n + \mathbf{C} \dot{\mathbf{u}}_n = \mathbf{F}_{ext} - \mathbf{F}_{int} \quad (5)$$

\mathbf{M} and \mathbf{C} are the mass and damping matrices, $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_n$ and $\dot{\mathbf{u}}_n$ are the nodal accelerations and velocities, \mathbf{F}_{ext} and \mathbf{F}_{int} are the nodal external and interior loads. Equation (5) is time integrated with an explicit method based on the central difference time step scheme.

The only term that is specific to the finite element simulation of fabric is the nodal interior load \mathbf{F}_{int} . It is the assembling of the elementary interior loads:

$$\mathbf{F}_{int} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{F}_{int}^e \quad (6)$$

with

$$\sum_{p=1}^{n_{\text{cell}}^e} (\boldsymbol{\eta}_n^e)^T \mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}^e = \sum_{p=1}^{n_{\text{cell}}^e} (\boldsymbol{\eta}_n^e)_s (\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}^e)_s = \sum_{p=1}^{n_{\text{cell}}^e} {}^p \varepsilon_{11}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{11} {}^p L_1 + {}^p \varepsilon_{22}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) {}^p T^{22} {}^p L_2 \quad (7)$$

The elements built in equation (7) are not based on the mechanics of continuous media where the behaviour relating the stress and the strain would correspond to the behaviour of a fibre fabric. They are discrete elements in which the strain energy of each elementary woven cell is added in the strain energy of the element.

Finite elements made of elementary cells.

The finite element that is presented as an example is a four node element which is made of n_{cell}^e woven elementary meshes (Figure 3). The warp and weft directions are the natural directions of the element. This is not compulsory, but it leads to an improved numerical efficiency. Most of the fabrics before forming are made of the assembly of rectangular parts. For more complicated initial fabric blanks, a three node triangular element has been developed [20].

Fig.3 Finite element made of wovens cells

This element uses the classical bilinear interpolation functions. The material coordinates ξ_1, ξ_2 are measured in the warp and weft yarn directions. They define initial material covariant vectors $\mathbf{g}_{10}, \mathbf{g}_{20}$, and current material covariant vectors $\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2$. In the case of the four node element, equation (7) leads to the following form of the components of the nodal elementary interior load :

$$(\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}}^e)_s = \sum_{\gamma=1}^2 \sum_{\delta=1}^2 \frac{n_c n_t}{4} \left(\bar{B}_{11s} L_{01} T^{11} \|\mathbf{g}_{10}\|^{-2} + \bar{B}_{22s} L_{02} T^{22} \|\mathbf{g}_{20}\|^{-2} \right) \quad (24)$$

where $\bar{B}_{\alpha\alpha s}$ are the components of the strain interpolation matrix such as :

$$\bar{B}_{\alpha\alpha s} = \frac{\partial N^k}{\partial \xi_\alpha} (\mathbf{g}_{\alpha 0})_m \quad \text{with } k = \text{integer} \left(\frac{s+2}{3} \right), \quad m = s-3(k+1) \quad (25)$$

This form is very simple and explicit. Consequently, the computations based on this element will be very fast. The only requested behaviour is the value of the two tensions (T^{11}, T^{22}) for two given strains ($\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22}$) within an elementary woven cell. It is given by the

knowledge of the biaxial mechanical behaviour surfaces as studied in the previous sections. This is close to the physics of the fabric and allows to introduce enhanced models for any kind of fabric.

Hemispherical fabric sheet forming simulation.

The element presented above has been implemented in the Pam-Form™ code [21, 22] which uses such an explicit approach as described above. A initially flat square fabric sheet is shaped in an hemispherical dome (Figures 4). The shaping simulation is made of two different fabrics. The first fabric is a balanced glass twill weave used for R.T.M. preforms in automotive industry [23]. The computed deformed shape (Figure 6) can be compared with good agreement to the experimental shape (Figure 5). Details on the comparison of the experimental and computed shapes can be found in [24]. A second fabric (also used in automotive industry) is considered. It has been designed to admit very large strains in the weft direction in order to be easily shaped on rubber parts. The stiffness in direction x is twenty times weaker than in direction y . The deformed shape is quite different from the shape of the balanced fabric (Figure 6).

Fig 4 Hemispherical fabric sheet forming

Fig 5 Experimental shape

Fig.6 Computed deformed shape

The mechanical properties of the fabric can have important consequences on the shaping result. It has also been shown [24] that the static boundary conditions, especially the loads on the blank holder, or the effects of drawbeads, can modify the shape after forming. This aspect cannot be taken into account by the geometrical draping algorithms.

CFRTP FORMING SIMULATION

Conception steps of thermoplastic composite. Experimental approach

The main advantages of using thermoplastic sheet composite in aeronautic industry are an infinite service life and a shorter fabrication cycle. The conception process could be resumed in three steps (figure 8). The first step consists to obtain, in a pressure vessel, plane plates of laminated (figure 7) constituted by several layers of reinforcements (UD or woven) linked by a thermoplastic resin. These plates are heated at the melting temperature of the resin and formed by a classical process with punch and die. Finally they are subjected to a re-compaction step by a pressure applied on the punch. During this manufacturing process the principal deformation comes from the sliding between the layers which allows to the sheet to be formed on the die. But the main default is the porosity at the interface of the layers.

Fig 7: Laminated composite

Fig 8: fabrication process of thermoplastic composite

The experimental approach consists during these steps to study the evolution of defaults on the laminated plates. The material studied is constituted by 10 layers of carbon fibers and a Peek resin. The layers's orientation is $[90, -45, 0, 45, 0]_s$ and each ply has a thickness of 0.135 mm. The tested shape is a longitudinal stiffener which has a Z form (figure 9)

Fig. 9: Z form of Longitudinal stiffener

Some micrographic cuts are analysed in several points of the laminated plate, in plane parts (parts 1 in figure 9) and in curvature radii (parts 2 in figure 9).

Simulations of the forming step.

Our first work consists to simulate the forming step of a Z longitudinal stiffener (figure 10). Each layer is associated to a shell layer. Sliding between layers is built in specific sliding law present in Pam-Form[®] code used [11]. With these simulations it's possible to analyse influence of parameters (stacking layers, tool's geometry) on the feasibility of the forming step and specially on the sliding of layers (figure 11). But with these simulations we couldn't take into account the re-compaction step, and the specific behaviour in bending for a material constituted by layers.

Fig. 10 Forming of a Z profile

Fig.11 Sliding between layers

Specific shell finite element for the re-compaction phase

The classical shell finite elements (normal stress component equal to zero) cannot be used during the consolidation step, because a pressure is applied on the laminated composite structure. We propose an approach, for the model of a ply, using a shell element with pinching not based on the classical hypothesis for the normal stress component [25, 26]. The main advantage of this element is to describe correctly the re-compaction step and the forming step with the same f.e. model.

In a shell finite element with pinching, the position of a point in it is defined by its projection on the reference surface and its position on the sub-normal:

$$\mathbf{x} = \bar{\mathbf{x}} + \tilde{z} \hat{\mathbf{X}} \quad (26)$$

Displacement of this point is obtained with the current and the initial position:

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} + \tilde{z}^t \hat{\mathbf{X}}^t - \tilde{z}^0 \hat{\mathbf{X}}^0 \quad (27)$$

If we denote the displacement component in the thickness of the point by Δh and by w the deformation in the thickness:

$$\Delta h = \tilde{z}^t - \tilde{z}^0 \quad (28)$$

$$w = \Delta h / \tilde{z}^0 \quad (29)$$

the displacement can be written :

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} + \tilde{z}^0 (\hat{\mathbf{X}}^t - \hat{\mathbf{X}}^0) + w \tilde{z}^0 \hat{\mathbf{X}}^t \quad (30)$$

the finite element interpolation has 6 degrees of freedom by node: 3 for the displacement of the point projected on the average surface, 2 for the rotation of the sub-normal et 1 for the strain in the thickness.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we propose a mechanical approach for the simulation of the forming processes of composite. For the RTM process our approach can take into account specificities of fabric's behaviour, or the influence of the static boundary which control the faisability of the forming step. By an analyse of the deformation process of the fabric during the forming step, this approach lead us to study the specific behaviour of the fabric. This biaxial behaviour is represented par biaxial surfaces behaviour linking tensions in the yarns to deformation state. Three approach [27] are used to define these surfaces and give good results. With this behaviour our study consists to build finite element consistent with this behaviour which are implemented in an industrial code PAM-FORM. For the conception of thermoplastic composite with continous fibers (CFRTP), if the simulation of the forming step are in good agreement with an experimental approach, it's necessary to developp a new shell element with pinching for the re-consolidation step. Furthermore for this process the analyse of the bending of a material constituted by fibers will be developed in a next paper.

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